

The Teachers' Strategy on Students' Communicative Ability Action Research

Suparman
STIT Palapa Nusantara Lombok NTB
Lalusuparman2@gmail.com

Abstract : The study aimed to find out the students' communicative ability and how far the students' improvement in communicative ability after getting the teaching and learning by using the appropriate teachers' strategy. It was the communicative strategy to solve the problem of how is the communicative ability and how does the communicative strategy improve the communicative ability of the students. The research was designed in a classroom action research which was done on three cycles. The practicum was performed in class eight grade 8B of MTs.Yaqin 2 Pemandah which had 34 learners. During the practice the main area taught was English using useful strategy to help the students in improving their communicative ability. The finding of the study on cycle one was 91.18%, meanwhile the hypothesis acceptance was 75 %. It was also happened on cycle two and three. According to the gained data on cycle two, the students' communicative ability reached 97,06%, and 100 % on cycle three. The gaining of the improvement of the students' communicative ability reached more than 81.18% on cycle one, on cycle two reached up to 87.06%, and on cycle three reached up to 90%. So that the application of the teachers' strategy in teaching and learning process may increase the students' communicative ability.

Key word: Teachers' strategy, communicative ability.

Introduction

No one can deny that people as human beings as well as social beings need to communicate to another by using the language. Language as social is needed as the medium of it. Language is the communication by voice in the distinctively human manner, using arbitrary sounds in conventional ways with conventional meanings¹. Language is a set of symbols being used mainly for communication. As a set of

¹ Dictionary Com" What is Language" Available : <http://www.dictionary.com/browse/language>
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symbols the language is used mainly for communication in the form of spoken or written. Language is an aspect of human behavior in spoken form is a means of communication. Language is the key aspect of human intelligence². Language, a system of conventional spoken, manual, or written symbols by means of which human beings, as members of a social group and participants in its culture, express themselves. The function of language include communication, the expression of identity, play, imaginative expression, and emotional release. In most accounts, the existence of the language take so important place in our daily life, because the primary purpose of language is to facilitate communication, in the sense of transmission of information from one person to another³.

English as an international language serves as a lingua franca and it is spoken, learnt and understood even in those countries where it is not a native's language. Besides English is playing a major role in many sectors including education, medicine, engineering, advanced studies, business, technology, banking, computing, tourism etc. As a result, English is being taught and learned around the world as a second language today. Since language is a tool of communication, we communicate with others, to express our ideas, and to know other's ideas as well. Communication takes place, where there is speech. Without speech we can not communicate with one another⁴.

In Indonesia, English as a second language, especially in educational concern which is taught nowadays formally from the primary school up to the university realizing that English as an international language has an important part in developing students' knowledge. It is taught in the form of four skills, listening, speaking, reading, and writing. The four language skills of listening, speaking, reading, and writing are all interconnected. Proficiency in each skill is necessary to become a well-rounded communicator, but the ability to speak skillfully provides the

² Robin[2013]"What is Language". Available: <http://language.worldofcomputing.net/linguistics/introduction/what-is-language.html>

³ David Crystal, Robert Henry Robins [2013]" Language ". Available: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/language>

⁴ Ishrat Aamer Qureshi, The Importance of Speaking skills for EFL Learners (online) Dep.of English Alama Iqbal Univ. Available: ishrataamer@hotmail.com

speaker with the distinct advantages of communicative ability. The capacity to put words together in meaningful way to reflect thoughts, opinions, and feelings provides the speaker with these important advantages, such as ; (1) ability to inform, persuade, and direct, (2) ability to stand out from the rest, (3) ability to benefit derivatively, and (4) career enhancement⁵.

In the real case of English language learning, however there is a problem which students have been aware of for a long time. It is the problem of the students who are structurally competent but who cannot communicate appropriately in speaking. In the other sides, the chosen strategy used by the teacher is not appropriately to support the students' communicative ability. As the problem occur overtime , it is essential for the teacher to change. As for the needs of the students and the suitable teaching strategy used in the classroom have to be applied accordingly. On the other hand the teachers should become more and more autonomous for the sake of providing the students with effective learning possibilities where the students come across their own potentialities to improve their ideal. As has been said, what happens in the classroom depends on the teachers' ability to maintain students' interest⁶ Thus A teacher should be a researcher in he classroom, the educational problems that arise in the classroom community should be solved by the teachers' intervention⁷.Sometime a very little in the intervention of the teacher solving a little problem may create a great influence on the learning process of the students, for example l teacher who does teaching according to her or his personal belief strategy about learning, will change her or his way of teaching with the results and experiences of a small action research⁸. Helping the students in developing the ability to communicate, a teacher should look for an effective strategy to make learning English easier, more pleasant, and more enjoyable. In order to overcome this problem the process involved communicative ability need to be dealt with by using the appropriate strategy to develop the ability to communicate.

⁵ Gerald Gillis [2013]"The importance of speaking skills ". Available : <http://www.geraldgillis.com/importance-speaking-skills/>

⁶ NYU STEINHARDT,Dept. of Teaching and Learning"The Effect of the Teachers'Style on students'Motivation Action Research"Available:<https://Steinhardt.nyu.edu>

⁷ British Council" Classroom Action Research " Available: <https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk/blog>

⁸ Ibid.

Hypothesis

If teachers' teaching strategy would fit in a class and is used appropriately, then students' communicative ability would increase.

Purpose of the Study

The main trust of the study was to find out the students' communicative ability and how far the students' improvement in communicative ability.

Action Research Questions

This paper attempted to answer specific questions such as : (1) to what extend is students' communicative ability? (2) How can the teachers' strategy improve the students' communicative ability?

Research Design / Methods of Collecting Data

The conducted research was Classroom Action Research. The taken model was the model of Mc Kernan, where the research involved the general idea in detail by identifying he problem of research questions, the purose of the study, and the stated of hypothesis⁹. It is more systematic than personal reflection but it is more informal and personal than formal educational research. Classroom Action Research is a method of finding out what works best in teachers' own classroom to improve students' learning¹⁰. The goal of classroom research is to improve the teachers' own teaching in the classroom, department, or school¹¹. The steps to conduct Classroom Action Research are; (1) identify a question or problem, (2) review literature, (3) plan a research strategy, (3) gather data, (4) make sense of the data, (5) take action, and (6) share the finding¹².

⁹ Hamid Darmadi [2011]"Metode penelitian pendidikan" Alfabeta Bandung

¹⁰ Julian Hermida from Gwyn Mettetal," The what, why, and how of CAR", Jo So TL Vol.2,Number 1(2001)

¹¹ Ibid

¹¹.Ibid

Research Environment and Respondents

The conducted research was at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Yaqin 2 Pemandah where three teachers conducting the research.. They were as the subject of the research . The students of these teachers own at seventh and eight graders were selected randomly, where ten to twelve students from each class were chosen. Thirty four students were taken as samples. To measure students' communicative ability, it was used teacher made test which covered important aspects of communicative ability. They are fluency, pronunciation, intonation, and structure / grammar . To get the data about the implementation of teaching and learning strategy was done by getting open observation by using the Likert scale in which arranged in 1 up to 5 score. The side who does the action in the real class is the real teacher, and the side who did the observation were the researcher who was assisted by the collaborator teacher in the form of collaboration and open observation¹³. Open observation in which the attendance of the observer in the classroom observation is open and well known by the presenter, so that there is a natural interaction between the researcher and the responder¹⁴. The instrument of observation of teachers' teaching strategy in teaching and learning covers various components such as : (1) preparation of teaching covers five components; (2) application of teaching covers sixteen components; and (3) evaluation covers five components. Besides, the data which were collected from this research guided the teachers to think and evaluate the strength and weaknesses of their own instruction to be improved.

Research Procedure

The teacher made test was implemented to gather the data. The maximum score was twenty. Each aspect of fluency, pronunciation, intonation, and structure / grammar ranges from one to five. The students score of communicative ability were

¹³ Suharsimi Arikunto [2013]"Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktek" Rineka Cipta

¹⁴ Hamid Darmadi [2011]"Metode penelitian pendidikan" Alfabeta Bandung.

collected in tables and interpreted using the simple percentage. The use of descriptive qualitative to analyze the mastery learning of the students by comparing the gaining score of students' communicative ability with the stated minimal criteria of mastery learning. The MCM (minimal criteria of mastery learning) is derived from calculating intake of students, degree of difficulty, and the resource support in implementing the teaching and learning process. The estimated MCM was 75%, where students' intake was 2, degree of difficulty was 2, and the resource support was 2.

Review of Related Literature

Communicative language teaching or the communicative approach is an approach to language teaching that emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of study¹⁵. The communicative approach is based on the idea that learning the language successfully comes through having to communicate real meaning. When learners are involved in real communication , their natural strategies for language acquisition will be used, and this will allow them to learn to use the language¹⁶. Some roles are assumed for teacher in communicative language teaching, are¹⁷ ; (1) to facilitate the communication process between all participants in the classroom, and between these participants and the various activities and texts, (2) to act as an independent participants within the learning teaching group. The concept of the communicative strategy in leaning second and foreign language is one of the most important. Within most language learning strategy taxonomies one of the most common categories is that of communication strategies. Communication strategies are strategies that learners employ when their communicative competence in the language is being learned. This include making themselves understood and having others help them understand¹⁸. There are three general situations that occur in and out of class where students need to be able to employ communication strategies, they are; (1) explaining word and phrases by wish to say when they do not know the

¹⁵ Communicative language teaching”Wikipedia” Available:<https://en.wikipedia.org>

¹⁶ “Communicative approach”. Available : <https://www.teachingenglish.org.uk>

¹⁷ “Communicative language taching”Available : www2.vobs.at/ludeshher/alternative%2

¹⁸ Jason Williams”Combining Communication Strategies and vocabularies” .Available:Jason williamsjp [at]yahoo.co.jp.

appropriate English; (2) reacting appropriately when they encounter a word or phrase in English that they are not familiar; (3) recognition and rectifying instances when they either use an English word incorrectly or use one of their partner is not familiar with¹⁹.

Furthermore, it was begun to identify some aspect and the climate of teaching and learning process. Research made by Shofiyyah Choirunnisa (2007) showed that the use of teaching and learning strategy by using communicative strategy could be employed to increase students' communicative ability.

Presentation, analysis and Interpretation of Data

To answer the subsidiary problem of the study, the research result were the data of classroom observation according to the implementation of teaching and learning strategy and the test result of students to measure the increase students' communicative ability. The data was analyzed by submitting the observation data taken while the process of teaching and learning was going on in every cycles.

Table 1 : The action quality of Teachers' Strategy in Teaching and Learning

Teachers' Activities	The taken Score of classroom observation						Total
	Cycle 1		Cycle 2		Cycle 3		
	Obs 1	Obs 2	Obs 1	Obs 2	Obs 1	Obs 2	
Preparation of teaching	27	28	28	30	30	30	173
Application of teaching	87	88	88	89	89	89	530
Evaluation	23	24	24	25	25	25	146
Total score	137	140	140	144	144	144	849
The maximum scores	145	145	145	145	145	145	870

¹⁹ Jason Williams"Combining Communication Strategies and vocabularies" .Available:Jason williamsjp [at]yahoo.co.jp.

The percentage	94.48.	96.55	96.55	99.31	99.31	99.31	585.510
	Average						97.586

Notes of qualification : 115.00 - 145.00 = very high

85.00 - 114.99 = high

50.00 - 84.99 = sufficient

35.00 - 49.99 = low

00.00 - 34.99 = very low

Based on the data above, the average percentage of teaching and learning by applying the teachers' strategy increase from cycle one up to cycle three. The average percentage on cycle one was 95.515. While the average percentage on cycle two was 97.93. At the end the average percentage on cycle 3 was 99.31. The average of total cycle was 97. 586. It can be concluded that the qualification is categorized into high qualification.

Table 2 : The data of students' communicative ability. It was gained after three cycles were given. It was used an instrument of oral test to get the data about students' communicative ability. The students were asked to converse in pairs. It was done three times chance.

Aspects	Students' score			Total
	Cycle 1	Cycle 2	Cycle 3	
Fluency	594	609	615	1.818
Pronunciation	610	616	617	1.843
Intonation	616	614	620	1.850
Structure	631	632	642	1.950
Total Score	2.451	2.471	2.494	7.461
Maximum score	3.400	3.400	3.400	10.200
Percentage Score	72.09	72.68	73.35	73.15

The data above was the recapitulation of students' communicative ability that was done in cycle one, cycle two and ended on cycle three.

Based on the presented data above, it was shown that the percentage of students' communicative ability was increased on each cycle. They were 72.09 on cycle one, 72.68 on cycle two, and 73.35 on cycle three. The average of the percentage of students' communicative ability was 73.15. If the research result of the second cycle is different from the research result on cycle one, the researcher need to do further cycle on the third cycle until the faithful and stable conclusion is got²⁰. After the third cycle was given, the researcher was firm that the data gained was faithful.

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- Robin[2013]”What is Lanuage”Retrieved from :<http://language.worldofcomputing.net/linguistics/introduction/what-is-language.html>. Visited on September 2018

²⁰ Suharsimi Arikunto [2013] “ *Prosedur Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktik*” Rineka Cipta Volume 6, Nomor 2, November 2018

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